

Application of Social Inquiry Learning Model to Improve Social Problem Solving Skills in Class IV Students of SD Gmit Bakitba

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Abstract: Elementary school is the initial foundation of all subsequent levels of schooling. In the process of forming character, skills and knowledge of students, one of the teacher's problems is how to choose learning media that matches the material being taught. The problem found is that the teacher has not developed learning that makes students active. This resulted in a boring learning atmosphere and Social Sciences (Social Studies) learning conducted by the teacher was still limited to rote material. Students are only treated to material without regard to other abilities that should be mastered by students. The research objective was to improve students' problem solving skills through the application of social inquiry learning models to fourth grade students at SD GMT Bakitba. Research using classroom action research methods. Data collection techniques are observation and tests. The results showed that the activities of students and teachers in the application of the social inquiry learning model showed increased results. Evidenced by an increase in learning activity in the first cycle of 87.5% increased in the second cycle to 100%, and in student activity in the first cycle of 75.8 and increased in the second cycle by 100%.

Keywords:- Learning models, social inquiry, elementary students, problem solving skills.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a very important component in the formation of a person's personality in facing the challenges of the times and the rapid advancement of technology. Djumali et al (2014: 1) argue that the purpose of education is to prepare humans to solve life's problems in the present and the future. In forming the personality and knowledge of students, it must be instilled from an early age so that learning for early childhood formally starts from the elementary school level.

According to Law no. 20 of 2003 Ministry of Education and Culture (Rahman, 2014) Learning is a system composed of various parts that are interconnected. These components include: objectives, materials, methods, strategies, and approaches to be used in learning activities. Learning is essentially a process of interaction between teachers and students, namely face-to-face activities between teachers and students as well as students and students. While learning indirectly, namely by using various learning media. Learning media is a communication tool in print and audio-visual form, including hardware technology and the role of learning media.

Elementary school is the starting point for all subsequent levels of education. In the process of forming character, skills and knowledge of students, one of the teacher's problems is how to choose learning media that matches the material being taught. According to Arsyad (2016: 2), media is an integral part of the teaching and learning process to achieve educational goals in general and to achieve learning goals in schools in particular. This means that the existence of learning media can attract students' interest in learning so that the desired learning objectives are achieved.

Piaget (Sagala, 2013) explains that education is a medium that unites social, intellectual and moral values, where the teacher/educator has the responsibility to align everything in the learning process in the classroom. Good learning occurs when there is intense two-way communication between students and learning resources, in this case teachers and students. We must leave the old educational paradigm of traditional learning, namely when the teacher becomes the dominant factor in the class (thought-centered learning).

Inquiry learning is a cycle. According to Amri and Ahmad (2010), the cycle consists of seven parts which include: moving from observation to understanding, students learn to use critical thinking, observation, make assumptions/conditional hypotheses. This research began when researchers made observations at GMT Bakitba Elementary School, on May 9 2023, at 09.00 WITA, especially in class IV. This initial observation uses questions and observations directed at students. The results of these observations indicate that Social Studies (Social Studies) learning conducted by teachers is still limited to rote material. Students are only treated to material without regard to other abilities that should be mastered by students.

In terms of the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) made by the class IV teacher, it is known that the indicators that must be achieved by students are still relatively low. The skills and competencies that students need to master are still limited to low-order thinking skills. So that students cannot develop their potential to be better. Most of the learning models used by teachers still use teacher-centered learning models. Most of the methods used are still using the lecture method. Teachers tend to dominate learning in the classroom. Teachers have not developed learning that makes students active. This results in a boring learning atmosphere. Learning activities do not encourage students to be active, both in solving problems and actively asking questions. Students only need to listen and write. If it is felt, then it is far from a

pleasant learning. Although teachers sometimes also use games to simply turn on the class to be enthusiastic and conducive. The media used by teachers in social studies learning is also very minimal. Evidenced by the very small number of media that can be observed by researchers.

Furthermore, from student recognition during the learning process, especially in social studies lessons, no other abilities or skills were developed. If seen from the students' notes it is clear, the contents of the notes are only limited to material and questions that develop low-level thinking skills. This is indicated by the poor quality of the questions, namely; what, who, where. Even if there are questions, how and why, to answer the students don't need to have trouble finding answers. Because the answer is already in the material provided by the teacher. When the researcher dug deeper into the student's abilities, the researcher found student answers that only led to the ability to memorize the material. Students only see the material provided by the teacher. Students do not develop their answers by thinking about them more deeply. That is, students are able to compile and produce their own answers by looking at and considering the factors that might occur when deciding to choose that answer. This is why the abilities or skills of students are less developed.

From these problems, there are consequences for students during the learning process, namely; (1) the low number of students who pass according to the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) in social studies subjects for class V which has been determined by the school is 70, out of 24 students who achieve KKM only 8 people or about 30% of the total, this means there are still many students whose abilities must be improved again, (2) the learning atmosphere is monotonous so that students quickly feel bored in participating in learning, (3) the learning atmosphere is less conducive because students are diverted to other activities such as; crowded, playing with the theme, and busy in activities other than taking lessons, (4) the low ability of students to develop higher-order thinking skills such as social problem solving skills. Therefore, it can be said that the ability to solve problems owned by students through learning is still low for students.

Taking into account the problems and consequences described above, the researcher assumes that the low skills of students are caused by several things, namely; (1) teachers do not develop learning that can facilitate students to be active, (2) teachers have not developed learning strategies that are appropriate to students' self-development including social problem solving skills, whose contents include appropriate learning models and methods, (3) teachers have not developed learning process that can improve a conducive learning atmosphere in accordance with the learning steps, (4) teachers have not developed learning that can improve students' skills, especially skills in solving social problems. More specifically, all of this is because teachers have not developed appropriate learning strategies, which contain learning models and methods.

Related to the analysis of Competency Standards (SK) and Basic Competency (KD) for social studies class IV, most students are required to master material about history. Students must master material about historical events, historical times, historical actors, and places where history occurred. In the first semester, KD is listed: (1.5 Recognizing the types of business and economic activities in Indonesia) which discusses the types of businesses and economic activities in Indonesia. Although students are introduced to the types of businesses and economic activities in Indonesia. Not that students only know, but also analyze economic problems and solve social problems. From a developmental point of view, grade IV is a period when students are able to use their minds in terms of critical thinking to solve social problems.

Based on the description of the problem above, to overcome this problem the researcher tried to apply the social inquiry learning model to improve social problem solving skills at GMIT Bakitba Elementary School, South Central Timor District. It is hoped that the application of the IPS learning model can improve students' skills in solving social problems. So that in the future a young generation will be born who are intelligent, tough, skilled and useful for the family, society, nation and state. Thus the researchers formulated this research with the title "*Application of the Social Sciences Learning Model to Improve the Social Problem Solving Skills of Grade IV SD GMIT Bakitba Students*".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Social Inquiry Learning Model

The social inquiry learning model is a learning model that adapts to student experiences. Then the school only contributes to the self-development of students on their own responsibility. The application of the social inquiry learning model is carried out by giving problems given by the teacher. Students will search for answers in a way that students can do, usually students will conduct research and be guided by the teacher or free students to find and solve problems on their own. (Sagala, Saiful, 2017). Seif (Ngalimun, 2013:33) states that research means knowing how to find something and how to know how to solve problems. Asking about something means seeking information, being curious, asking questions, researching and acquiring skills that help him solve problems.

B. The characteristics of the Social Inquiry Learning Model

According to Julianto *et al* (2011: 90), inquiry learning has several characteristics, including:

- The inquiry learning model emphasizes maximum student activity to seek and find.
- All activities carried out by students are directed to seek and find their own answers to something in question, so that it is hoped that they can foster self-confidence (self-belief).
- The purpose of using inquiry learning is to develop the ability to think systematically, logically and critically, or to develop intellectual abilities as part of a mental process.

C. The Purpose of the Social Inquiry Learning Model

According to Jarolimek (in Ngalimun, 2013: 35), the main purpose of inquiry-based learning is to develop students' attitudes and skills to become independent problem solvers.

D. Social Problem Solving Skills

Cartledge and Milburn (in Maryani, 2011: 17) explain that social skills are attitudes that must be learned because they allow individuals to interact to obtain positive and negative responses. Meanwhile Maryani (2011: 18) states that social skills are the ability to interact, communicate and participate in groups, this needs to be supported by personal intelligence, in the form of self-control, self-confidence, discipline and responsibility in order to create harmonious cooperation between individuals. Social skills are very necessary and must be a priority in teaching, teaching is not just developing academic skills, but also developing social skills, teachers must work together with parents in determining what skills should be prioritized, choosing one of the social skills, explaining the importance social skills, and practice them (Cadler in Maryani, 2011: 19). Because social skills can support the success of social relations and enable individuals to work together with others effectively (Samanci, 2010).

E. Steps in Solving Social Problems

Bransford and Stein (in Santrock, 2010: 371) suggest that efforts have been made to specify the steps that individuals must go through to solve problems or problems effectively, here are four steps in solving problems:

- Find and understand the problem.
- Develop a good problem solving strategy
- Explore solutions
- Rethinking and reformulating problems and solutions from time to time.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a type of qualitative research that uses a classroom action research design conducted in the classroom, with the aim of improving results, quality and teaching systems. Will it be improved after the research is carried out or not? In this study, researchers used data collection techniques in the form of observations, tests, and student response questionnaires. In this study, to analyze the data, researchers used descriptive analysis techniques and statistical analysis techniques.

This is in accordance with what was revealed by Trianto (2011: 13), this research uses Classroom Action Research (CAR), namely research conducted in a class to find out the effects of actions applied to a research subject in that class. The researcher made initial observations to find out the problems in class IV. The researcher observed the activities of the teacher who was teaching, asked questions addressed to students, and looked at various facts. The aim is to find out the real problems that occur in the class. In addition, researchers also conducted discussions and analysis of competency standards and basic competencies. Where the results of this analysis will be used by researchers when the research process takes place. The goal is to find out the suitability of the field of study to be studied with the main

objectives to be achieved by the researcher. So that in the implementation of the research there was no misunderstanding between the researcher and the class teacher. Besides that, later the material used by researchers is in accordance with what is expected. This study uses a research design developed by Kemmis Mc. Taggart. Each cycle includes: (1) planning, (2) acting, (3) observing, and (4) reflecting. The next cycle steps are planning revision, action, observation and reflection.

Below is a spiral cycle of the stages of classroom action research which can be seen in the following chart:

A. The planning phase includes:

Determining, analyzing, reviewing and studying SK and KD social studies class IV subjects, preparing lesson plans to be used in the teaching process, determining learning media, compiling teacher and student activity observation sheets, making questionnaires, to find out how the response of students after social studies learning, Develop learning evaluation tools Develop learning evaluation tool.

B. Action and Observation Stage

After preparing and planning activities from various tools and materials that will be used in learning. The next step is the implementation of the action itself. The steps taken by the researcher in accordance with the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) include the following:

- *Initial activity*
 - The teacher opens the lesson by greeting and checking student attendance.
 - The teacher conditions students to be ready to accept the subject matter, namely by asking students to prepare their stationery and books.
 - Doing contracts and learning agreements with students.
- *Conveying learning objectives, namely getting to know social problems that exist in the environment related to social problems around students.*
- *Core activities*
 - The teacher explains the kinds of social problems that exist in the surrounding environment.
 - The teacher shows various problems that occur in the surrounding environment.
 - The teacher explains how to respond, analyze, and solve social problems in language that is easily understood by students.
 - Students are asked to observe social problems in their environment and try to respond, analyze, and solve these social problems.
 - The teacher distributes LKS to students and is guided in working on LKS.
 - Students are given the opportunity to communicate the results they get.
- *End activities*
 - Students are given an evaluation sheet and asked to work on it.
 - Students and teachers conclude learning outcomes
 - The teacher closes the lesson

At the implementation stage of this action all events that appear are observed and assessed by the observer. Where the observation sheet has been provided by the researcher. Furthermore, to find out student responses to the learning process, the researcher gave a student response questionnaire, which had previously been provided by the researcher.

C. Reflection Stage

At this reflection stage the researcher collected various data, which included observation sheets of teacher activity, student activity sheets during the learning process, sheets for improving students' social problem solving skills, and student response questionnaires. All of these data are put together for later analysis by researchers. After the data analysis activities were completed, the researcher and the class teacher held discussions to find out what the strengths and weaknesses were in that cycle. What obstacles and what successes have been obtained during the ongoing learning process. When researchers and teachers already know the results, the next step is to correct any deficiencies that existed in the previous learning process. The hope is to improve the quality of teaching and student learning outcomes, so that later it will experience an increase.

After everything has been evaluated by the researcher, for the next stage cycle 2 or cycle 3 the flow of research implementation is the same as that done in cycle 1. The activities include: (1) the planning stage, which contains all the needs and needs of both the syllabus, the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP), media, observation sheets, questionnaires, and evaluation sheets, (2) the class action stage, which contains a series of learning activities carried out by the teacher in the classroom, including initial activities, core activities, and closing activities of learning, (3) reflection stage, which contains the activities of collecting and analyzing research data to then look for its strengths and weaknesses in order to improve it. And so on, the flow of research is repeated until it finds perfection.

After data collection, the researcher conducted data analysis as follow:

$$P = \frac{f}{100}$$

Information:

P = percentage of times the event occurs

F = the number of teacher activities that appear

N = the total number of activities (Indarti, 2008:26)

The observation results are compared with the assessment criteria below:

≥ 80% = very high 60% - 79% = high

40% - 59% = moderate

20% - 39% = low

≤ 20% = very low (Aqib et al, 2011: 41)

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study will be presented in each cycle, where each cycle has two face-to-face teaching sessions. All incidents concerning the application of the social inquiry learning model to improve problem solving skills in Grade

IV students of SD GMIT Bakitba will be recorded and analyzed using the instruments provided. The aim is to facilitate data processing and determine improvements in the next cycle.

A. The results of the implementation of cycle I

➤ Planning

• Analyzing the curriculum

In accordance with the learning objectives, this research is to achieve success in accordance with basic competencies. The researcher conducted an analysis with the aim of finding suitability and feasibility between the material to be presented and the questions students would be working on to improve problem-solving skills. Thus, in the learning process there is harmony between the material provided by the teacher and the understanding obtained by students. To make their task easier, the researcher coordinated and consulted with the fourth grade teacher at SD GMIT Bakitba, Dra. Emy. The activity of conducting curriculum analysis is expected to facilitate the task of a researcher in terms of providing understanding and skills to students. Thus, everything that can hinder this research can be minimized as early as possible. Because indeed with all the shortcomings of researchers in knowing students from all aspects is very limited. Because the class teacher is the one who knows the real situation about the students.

• Develop lesson plans

After the researcher conducted a curriculum analysis, the researcher then developed it in the form of a lesson plan. The contents include: research time, preparing lesson plans, compiling student activity sheets, assessment sheets, and compiling research instruments.

• Determine the time of research

In this first cycle the researcher made an agreement with the class teacher. The aim is to determine the teacher's teaching schedule with the researcher's schedule. It is hoped that later there will be no misunderstanding in carrying out the task between the teacher and the researcher.

• Compile RPP (Learning Implementation Plan)

The researcher compiled the lesson plans containing: competency standards, basic competencies, indicators, learning objectives, learning activities, subject matter, learning media and tools, learning resources.

• Learning objectives are determined based on the learning indicators to be achieved.

Learning activities are arranged by researchers according to the syntax of social inquiry learning models that lead to skills in solving social problems. The learning activities contain the sequence or stages of all teacher activities from the introduction to closing the learning

activities and student activities when participating in the learning process. From harmony between teachers and students, problem solving skills will be achieved. The main material used is about social issues related to business and economic activities. The media used in this research uses media pictures about social problems, while the tools used are markers, erasers, and whiteboards. The learning resources used are pictures, student books, and the environment around students related to social issues.

- **Compile Student Activity Sheets (LKS)**

In compiling this LKS, the researcher adjusted it to the learning material that would be mastered by students. The LKS contains pictures of social problems followed by illustrations or brief descriptions to make it easier for students to understand the pictures. Followed by questions that lead to problem solving skills. The questions are arranged from easy level to difficult level. The goal is to train students from each stage correctly in solving social problems. Students follow the LKS in groups. Students will learn how to solve a social problem with other people. Which aspect has a value range of 0-4. The teacher gets a score of 4 if all rubrics are applied, 3 if 3 rubrics are applied, 2 if 2 rubrics are applied, and 1 if 1 rubric is applied, and a score of 0 if no rubric is applied.

- **Prepare assessment sheets**

In compiling this assessment sheet, the researcher also considered the suitability and feasibility of the material presented. It contains questions that require detailed answers. The questions are arranged from easy to difficult levels. The questions lead to skills in solving social problems. This assessment sheet will be done individually by students. This is done to determine the ability of each student in solving social problems.

- **Develop research instruments**

Based on the formulation of the problems that have been prepared previously, this research focuses on describing teacher activities, student activities, and improving student problem solving skills, as well as student responses to the learning that has been carried out by the teacher. In detail will be explained as follows; (1) Teacher activity observation sheet; This teacher activity observation sheet is structured to find out all teacher activities in learning. This instrument is adapted to the syntax of the social inquiry learning model. The teacher's activities from opening the lesson to closing the lesson will be observed without exception. This teacher activity observation sheet consists of aspects of the learning process, scoring rubrics and scores. In it there are 17 aspects from the beginning of learning to the end of learning. Each aspect will contain a rubric for its assessment. Where in one aspect there is a value range of 0-4. The teacher will get a score of 4 if all rubrics are implemented, get a score of 3 if 3 rubrics are implemented, get a score of 2 if 2 rubrics are implemented, and get a score of 1 if 1 rubric is implemented, and get a score of 0 if no rubric is implemented at all, (2) Student activity observation sheets; This student activity sheet is

structured to determine the extent of student activity in learning. All student activities during the learning process will be recorded in accordance with predetermined instruments. This instrument consists of; aspects, indicators, and scores. Each consists of 14 aspects, one aspect contains 4 indicators and will be followed by an assessment on score column. These aspects include; 1) listen to the teacher's explanation, 2) propose opinions, 3) answer questions, 4) work in groups, 5) analyze problems, 6) formulate problems, 7) make hypotheses, 8) collect evidence and facts, 9) test hypotheses, 10) solving problems and conclusions, 11) evaluating the results of solving problems, 12) presenting the results of group work, 13) concluding learning, 14) working on evaluation sheets. Which aspect has a value range of 0- 4. Students get a score of 4 if all rubrics are applied, 3 if 3 rubrics are applied, 2 if 2 rubrics are applied, 1 if one rubric is applied, and 0 if no rubric is applied.

- **Implementation**

After all the preparatory stages have been completed, the next stage is implementation. At this stage the researcher will carry out research in the classroom with two observers observing him. Researchers will conduct learning according to the syntax of the social inquiry learning model. Starting with the opening, explaining the material, giving examples to students on how to solve problems, forming groups, guiding students to understand the problem, guiding students to formulate problems, guiding students to make hypotheses, guiding students to collect evidence and facts, guiding students to test hypotheses, and conclusions. Each cycle has two meetings, for cycle 1 at meeting I discuss orientation, formulate problems and formulate hypotheses. While the second meeting discussed collecting data, testing hypotheses and concluding. In order to make learning easier, the researcher first formed study groups, while the groups can be seen in the following table.

Table 1: Observation Results of Cycle I Teacher Activities

Number	Aspects Observed Score	Score			
		O1	O2	RT	%
1.	Open learning	4	4	4	100
2.	Give apperception	4	4	4	100
3.	Delivering learning objectives	4	4	4	100
4.	Making learning contracts	4	4	4	100
5.	Explain material	4	4	4	100
6.	Forming groups	4	3	3,5	87,5
7.	Guiding students to analyze problems	2	3	2,5	62,5
8.	Guiding students to formulate the problem	3	3	3	87,5
9.	Guiding students to make hypotheses	3	3	3	75
10.	Guiding students to collect evidence and facts	3	2	2,5	62,5
11.	Guide students to test hypotheses	4	4	4	60
12.	Guiding students to determine problem solving	4	4	4	60
13.	Guiding students to convey the results of their group performance	3	4	3,5	87,5
14.	Guiding students to make learning conclusions	3	4	3,5	87,5
15.	Gives reinforcement	4	4	4	60
16.	Giving assignments as follow- up	4	4	4	60
17.	Close learning	4	4	4	100
	Final Grade	61	62	61,5	740
	Average	6,5	3,6	3,6	70

Information:

O1 = Observer I (Dra. Emy Wahyu Yulianti) O2 = Observer II (Midya Yuli Amreta)

RT = Average Criteria:

≥ 80% = very high 60% - 79% = high 40%-59%=moderate

20%-39%=low

≤ 20% = very low

Table 2 data is calculated using the formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100 = 70\% \text{ (high)}$$

The percentage of achievement of teacher activity in learning cycle I using the social inquiry learning model can be seen in graph 1 below:

Graph 1: The social inquiry learning model

Information:

- 1 = Open the lesson
- 2 = Give apperception
- 3= Convey learning objectives 4= Make learning

contracts

- 5 = Explain the material 6= Form a group
- 7= Guide students to analyze problems 8= Guide

students to formulate problems 9= Guide students to make hypotheses

10= Guide students to collect facts and evidence 11= Guide students to test hypotheses

12 = Guiding students to determine problem solving

13 = Guiding students to convey the results of group

performance

14 = Guiding students to make learning conclusions

15 = Provide reinforcement

16 = Giving assignments as a follow-up

17 = Closing the lesson

If seen in graphs 1-17 it gets a score of 87.5%, aspects (1) opening the lesson, (2) giving apperception, (3) conveying the learning objectives, (4) making a learning contract, (5) explaining the material, (6) forming groups, (7) guiding

students to analyze problems, (8) guiding students to formulate problems, (9) guiding students to make hypotheses, (10) guiding students to collect facts and evidence, (11) guiding students to test hypotheses, (12) guiding students to determine the most appropriate problem solving, (13) guiding students to convey the results of group performance, (14) guiding students to conclude learning, (15) providing reinforcement, at this stage the teacher obtains a score of 100% with a very high predicate, (16) gives assignment as a follow-up, at this stage the teacher obtains a score of 100% with a very high predicate, (17) provides learning, the lowest aspect is shown in analyzing problems, making hypotheses, and gathering evidence and facts.

• Cycle II

Based on the table, all aspects of teacher activity have been carried out. The teacher's success in teaching reaches 90%, getting a very high predicate. The teacher has been said to be successful, because learning has exceeded 80% according to the predetermined target. Even though the teacher's activities have been said to have been successful, rakes must improve the quality of their learning because there are several aspects that are still low and need to be improved.

Table 2: Results of Cycle II Student Activities

Number	Aspects Observed Score	Score			
		O1	O2	RT	%
1.	Open learning	4	4	4	100
2.	Give apperception	4	4	4	100
3.	Delivering learning objectives	4	4	4	100
4.	Making learning contracts	4	4	4	100
5.	Explain material	4	4	4	100
6.	Forming groups	4	3	3,5	87,5
7.	Guiding students to analyze problems	2	3	2,5	100
8.	Guiding students to formulate the problem	3	3	3	87,5
9.	Guiding students to make hypotheses	3	3	3	75
10.	Guiding students to collect evidence and facts	3	2	2,5	100
11.	Guide students to test hypotheses	4	4	4	87,5
12.	Guiding students to determine problem solving	4	4	4	60
13.	Guiding students to convey the results of their group performance	3	4	3,5	100
14.	Guiding students to make learning conclusions	3	4	3,5	100
15.	Gives reinforcement	4	4	4	100
16.	Giving assignments as follow-up	4	4	4	100
17.	Close learning	4	4	4	100
	Final Grade	66	66	66	1650
	Average	3,8	3,8	3,8	97

Table data is calculated using the formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

$$P = \frac{66}{4 \times 17} \times 100$$

$$= 97\% \text{ (very high)}$$

Graph 2: Teachers activity

If seen in graph 2, aspects 1-17 all aspects get a score of 100% with a very high rating.

The percentage of student activity in learning activities with the social inquiry learning model can be seen in graph 3 below:

Graph 3: Observation results of Student Activity Cycle I

Information:

- 1= Listen to the teacher's explanation
- 2= Propose an opinion
- 3= Answer questions
- 4= Work in groups
- 5= Analyze problems
- 6 = Formulate the problem
- 7= Making a hypothesis
- 8= Gathering evidence and facts
- 9= testing hypotheses

- 10 = Solving problems and conclusions
- 11= Evaluating the results of problem solving
- 12= Presenting the results of group work
- 13= Concluding learning
- 14= Doing an evaluation sheet

If seen in graph 3 aspects 1-14 students get a score of 87.5%.

Table 3: Observation results of Cycle I Student Activities

No	Aspects Observed Score	Score			
		O1	O2	RT	%
1.	Listen to the teacher's explanation	4	3	3,5	87,5
2.	Proposing opinions	4	4	4	100
3.	Answer questions	4	4	4	100
4.	Working in groups	4	3	3,5	87,5
5.	Analyze the problem	2	2	2	50
6.	Formulate the problem	4	4	4	100
7.	Make a hypothesis	3	2	2,5	62,5
8.	Gather evidence and facts	4	4	4	100
9.	Testing the hypothesis	3	3	3	75
10.	Solving problems and conclusions	4	4	4	100
11.	Evaluating the results of problem solving	3	3	3	75
12.	Presenting the results of group work	4	3	3,5	87,5
13.	Conclude learning	4	4	4	100
14.	Working on evaluation sheets	4	3	3,5	87,5
	Final Grade	51	46	42,5	1212,5

Table 3 data is calculated using the formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\% = \frac{42,5}{4 \times 14} \times 100 = 75,8$$

Table 4: Observation

No	Aspects Observed Score	Score			
		O1	O2	RT	%
1.	Listen to the teacher's explanation	4	3	3,5	100
2.	Proposing opinions	4	4	4	100
3.	Answer questions	4	4	4	100
4.	Working in groups	4	3	3,5	100
5.	Analyze the problem	2	2	2	62,5
6.	Formulate the problem	4	4	4	100
7.	Make a hypothesis	3	2	2,5	75
8.	Gather evidence and facts	4	4	4	87,5
9.	Testing the hypothesis	3	3	3	87,5
10.	Solving problems and conclusions	4	4	4	87,5

Results of Cycle II Student Activities

Table 4 data is calculated using the formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

$$P = \frac{51}{4 \times 14} \times 100 = 91\%$$

Graph 4: Observation results of Student Activity Cycle II

V. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

Teacher activity in teaching using the social inquiry learning model shows increased results. The activity with the highest score lies in the aspect of guiding students to analyze problems, guiding students to collect facts and evidence, and guiding students to determine problem solving.

The increase in these results is indicated by the performance of students in observing teacher learning with the social research learning model. The aspect of student activity with the highest score lies in formulating problems, collecting evidence and facts, and concluding learning. Student responses to teacher learning through the social inquiry learning model have shown good results. The biggest feedback is that students feel happy participating in learning, want to express their opinions, want to learn about social problems and their solutions and understand the material.

B. Advice

In applying each chosen learning model, the teacher must be able to adapt it to the material that will be delivered to students. The way the teacher must really understand the learning model that will be applied in learning activities. Before the teacher teaches directly to students, the teacher must plan it carefully. Teachers should read and understand the subject matter with the model that will be applied to learning. After the teacher really understands at that time, he then practices it directly in class.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Amri, Sofan and Iif Khoiru Ahmadi. 2010. Creative and Innovative Learning Processes in the Classroom. 2010. Jakarta: PT. Library Achievement.
- [2.] Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2010. Research Procedures A Practice Approach. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [3.] Arshad, Azhar. (2016). Learning Media, PT Raja Grafindo Persada: Jakarta
- [4.] Ministry of National Education. Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. Jakarta: Ministry of National Education.
- [5.] Djumali, et al. (2014). Educational Foundation. Bandung: Erlangga.
- [6.] Hilmi. (2017). Implementation of IPS Education in Social Studies Learning in Schools. Mandala Education Scientific journal, Vol. 3. No. 2. Accessed 12 February 2023.
- [7.] Julianto et al. 2011. Theory and Implementation of Innovative Learning Models. Surabaya:
- [8.] Maryani. (2011). Development of IPS Learning Programs for Improving Social Skills. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [9.] Craving. 2013. Learning Strategies and Models. Yogyakarta: Aswaja Presindo.
- [10.] Permendiknas No. 22 of 2006 concerning Content Standards, Permendikbud: Jakarta.
- [11.] Sagala, Saiful. (2013). The Concept and Meaning of Learning. Alfabeta. Bandung.
- [12.] Sagala, Saiful. (2017). The Concept and Meaning of Learning to Help Solve Problems of Teaching and Learning Problems (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2017).
- [13.] Samanci, O. (2010). Teacher Views on Social Skills Development Primary School Students. Education, 131 (1), p.147-157.
- [14.] Sapriya. (2014). Social Studies Education, PT Juvenile Rosdakarya: Bandung Susanto, M. (2013). Learning and Learning Theory in Elementary Schools. Jakarta Prenada Media Group. Unesa University Press.
- [15.] Santrock, John W. 2007. Educational Psychology. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.